

Summary results of Southern Great Plain case study (CS3)

Policy Brief

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Rethinking Southern Great Plain region in a changing climate

Key findings

- Stakeholder-based co-creation approach proved to be an effective method and working tool.
- Climate change will intensify the current risk with increased rainfall variability and localized water scarcity problems.
- Upgrade on-farm irrigation practices, minimize conveyance losses, and prioritize maintenance of regional water infrastructure to improve water-use efficiency in agriculture.
- Precision agriculture optimises allocation inputs and timing to lower water and fertiliser needs, which reduces N₂O and CO₂ emissions.
- Regenerative agriculture improves soil structure and infiltration to enhance drought resilience and reduce input dependency.
- Protecting or restoring infiltration areas and grasslands can enable temporary inundation and better recharge where suitable; integrate with spatial planning to retain water in the landscape.
- Strengthening multi-level coordination, data transparency and access to finance for farmers and municipalities is necessary to mainstream adaptive practices.

Keywords: Southern Great Plain Region; land-use; LAMS; water security; agriculture; system dynamics; adaptation; mitigation; implementing climate solutions.

Executive Summary

Hungary's Southern Great Plain is characterised by extensive cropland/grassland mosaics in a continental climate. Summer precipitation is declining and more uneven, while the number of hot days during the growing season increases. Sectoral water demand is rising, putting pressure on surface and groundwater systems. Agriculture is both the most exposed and the most influential sector for regional resilience. This policy brief distils stakeholder-selected **land-based adaptation and mitigation solutions (LAMS)** that keep development within ecosystem limits while advancing decarbonisation.

Source: [Mozaqsvilag](https://www.mozaqsvilag.com)

It outlines practical options to strengthen water security and upscale climate-smart farming. The Southern Great Plain case study focuses on drought and water scarcity, with agriculture as a pivotal sector. The brief targets regional policymakers, local authorities, farmer cooperatives, tourism operators, and energy planners.

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Background & Policy Context

Climate change is a risk multiplier that can exacerbate existing risks and crises through the interaction between climatic and non-climatic drivers. This includes land use change, which plays a crucial role in achieving the ambitious targets for climate resilience and climate neutrality in the European Union (EU) by 2050, as outlined in the framework of the EU Green Deal strategy ([Chiriaco et al., 2025](#)¹). The RethinkAction project supports the objectives of the EU Green Deal. In this context, the RethinkAction (H2020) project co-develops land-use-based adaptation and mitigation solutions (LAMS) with stakeholders across six EU case studies to reduce land-use-based emissions from various land-use types.

¹ Chiriaco, M.V. et al. (2025). A catalogue of land-based adaptation and mitigation solutions to tackle climate change. *Sci Data* 12, 166 [[doi](#)].

The Southern Great Plain Region is one of the six RethinkAction case studies exploring different LAMS to support the EU Green Deal target. The region faces freshwater scarcity and drought-driven yield losses, worsened by outdated infrastructure, weak coordination, and limited adaptive practices. Agriculture dominates with croplands, while grasslands and riparian zones support infiltration and drought buffering. Soil management is key, as hotter summers and irregular rainfall drive irrigation demand, intensify drought, and reduce yields and ecosystem services.

High-resolution land use map of the **Southern Great Plain**. Source: RethinkAction project.

Air temperature for historical period (1985-2014). Source: [RethinkAction Platform](#)

Climate & Geographic Focus for LAMS

The Southern Great Plain’s climate is influenced by two more or less permanent action centres of the temperate zone, the Icelandic Low and the Azores High. Depressions originating from the Iceland zone travel across the country, bringing cool weather and rain. When the Azores high gains ascendancy, the weather is bright and dry, both winter and summer. The average hours of sunshine is around 2000 hours a year in the region and the maxima is in July. The heat total during Hungary’s growing season rises above 3,000 °C over much of the country, which is very favorable to agriculture in Hungary, but frosts in April, May can present a serious hazard to crops in general. Increased water demand during the summer season can stress local water utility systems and the heat and dry waves (drought) put a pressure on productivity of lands.

Land-based Adaptation and Mitigation Solutions (LAMS) were prioritized by stakeholders and are central to ensure that Valle d’Aosta remains productive, climate-resilient, and ecologically sustainable.

Bridging Science and Society for Climate-Resilience Development

RethinkAction used state-of-the-art tools to connect climate scenarios with land-use decisions and policy options. The applied methodology combined climate modelling, land-use analysis, stakeholder engagement, and System Dynamics modelling to co-design actionable pathways. A participatory, multi-scale approach was applied, combining quantitative modelling with multiple stakeholder co-creation workshops across six case studies to evaluate different future alternatives.

Data collection, modelling, and policy analysis were carried out. A total of five basic *Essential Climate Variables* (Basic-ECVs) and 24 Derived-ECVs were downscaled to assess future exposures, followed by the identification of suitable LAMS based on both a literature review and multicriteria analysis, and their suitability at the local scale. Local stakeholders were involved in the evaluation of the potential risks across sectors through impact chains and the selection of potential packages of solutions, along with the main potential drivers and barriers of the region.

Local Workshop in Southern Great Plain region. Source: RethinkAction project.

The used Shared Socio-Economic Pathways (SSPs) were SSP1-2.6 (with lower emissions), SSP2-4.5 (with mid-range emissions) and SSP5-8.5 (highest emissions)

Translating Data into Action

Future climate trends for the Southern Great Plain suggest a continuous increase in drought experiencing in the summer terms (decreasing and uneven precipitation patterns combined with elevating temperatures). The water flows (rivers) are expected to maintain quantity, but fluctuating and to be more hectic, as flooding events could rise as well (occurrence and severity).

Temperatures expected to increase up to +8°C by 2100 under SSP5-8.5. A shift to a more hectic Spring term in terms of temperature is expected, resulting in +/- 7 C changes coinciding with the start of reproductive terms in vegetation. These trends will further increase the pressure on the local water regime and management system. Ecosystems are expected to experience increased water stress and drought effects, hence to have troubled delivery of ecosystem services. The drought affecting groundwater reserves in the summer causes risks towards drinking water supply and irrigation, while the system is burdened with large water consumers as well from the industrial sector. The agricultural sector would face increasing losses in case of flagship products i.e. maize. Though wheat can tolerate and probably even profit from the warmer climate in shorter run (winter wheat), the yields will be at risk.

Anomalies of precipitation for Southern Great Plain comparing the period 2071-2100 to the historical period (1985 - 2015) for SSP 1.2.6, 2.4.5 and 5.8.5. Source: RethinkAction project.

The climatic trends also have negative effects on the land and soils directly, posing risk in the current land management practices. Other sectors like manufacturing, with major plants in the region, will likely expect periods of shortages in water. These changes create multiple interconnected risks for the

Considering the most relevant risks, stakeholders had chosen specific LAMS for water management and agriculture sectors. The LAMS displayed are “Water use efficiency: improve agriculture irrigation efficiency”, “Water harvesting: collect and store rainwater in reservoirs” and “Protecting and restoring wetlands/grasslands”.

Local SD Model – Simulation Results

Water supply in Southern Great Plain, under medium policy intensity, for different SSP scenarios.

Impact chains were used to analyse these complex vulnerable conditions, considering all the factors involved. They are a tool that considers all the risk components and synthesizes the complex connections between them. They were quantified in the project following (Barilari et al., 2025²) and the results are available in the *RethinkAction platform*. One *impact chain* was developed to describe the risk in the agriculture sector: **Risk of agricultural yield loss due to drought**, influenced by biophysical, climatic, social, and institutional factors.

Stakeholder-Chosen LAMS

Water use efficiency: agriculture irrigation	Water harvesting	Protection of wetlands/grassland

Conclusions

The local analysis of the Southern Great Plain region shows a high sensitivity to climate change that manifests in different forms of risk. Drought effects and connected yield losses in the agriculture sector, are the most striking ones, and future exacerbation can be expected based on climatic trends, but also multiple barriers in the system on the social, institutional and policy levels. Major improvements will be needed in the local institutional domain, lack of harmonization among the water-agro-ecosystem support sectors, market uncertainties and generally eroded social trust. This will help to improve the resilience of the region against climate change and derived impacts and risks.

The key outcomes described in this brief are available in the Resources section of the *RethinkAction website* and in the *RethinkAction platform*.

Quantified risk through Impact Chains in Southern Great Plain for agriculture sector. Source: RethinkAction project.

² Barilari, S. et al. (2025). Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment in the Province of Almeria (Spain) Under Different Climate Change Scenarios. *Climate*, 13(7), 141. [doi].

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